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ROUTES TO SEMICONDUCTING POLY[n]CATENANES FROM CYCLOPARAPHENYLENES VIA BREAKABLE
DIRECTIVE IMIDE BONDS

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Possible ways to high molecular weight semiconducting poly[n]catenanes from cycloparaphenylenes discussed.

Space of mechanically interlocked molecules (MIMs) is separate and novel area of Chemical Space. Topological bond allow combine incompatible before properties of materials, so synthesis of mechanically interlocked polymers open new horizons for industry and progress in general [Ref.1].

Poly[n]Catenanes are objects of chemical competition still. A record-breaking poly[n]catenane synthesized by Qiong Wu et al. in Rowan Group [Ref.2]. One of the applicable techniques of polycatenane synthesis is covalent directing bonds, which proved by Schill [Ref.3], Godt [Ref.4] and Itami & Segawa [Ref.5], synthesized catenanes from cycloparaphenylenes. But high degrees of polycatenanization and high molecular weight were not achieved yet.

On the other hand, cycloparaphenylenes were a breakthrough in space of semiconducting organic molecules with unique optoelectronic properties [Ref.6]. Since first synthesis in 2008 by Ramesh Jasti and Carolyn Bertozzi [Ref.7], cycloparaphenylenic way in optoelectronics seems like one of the most promising. We can try uniting both novel (cycloparaphenylenes and polycatenanes) areas in one. Because of it, further searching of effective strategies retain their relevance as before and discussions continue.

DISCUSSION

General Strategy (idealized) shown in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3 (as described earlier [Ref.36]):

- 1) Face-to-face orientation of rigid-rod side chains (from rigid-rod main chain) with their mutual bonding and then destruction of main chain (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

- 2) Rigidity provides linearity and limitations of molecular mobility (axial rotations with minimal swings) - i.e desired direction (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

Figure 2.

- 3) Ideal nodal (directive) bond must be rigid-rod, planar, atropisomeric, easy to forming, selectively destructible (Figure 2).
- 4) Rotational energy barriers of Free Rotation Segments must be minimal [Ref.8], to facilitate face-to-face bonding of side chains (Figure 3).

Figure 3.

Cyclic imide bond chosen as directive bond in example of rout, which demonstrate main chain forming at first, then bonding to main chain of side chains and then coupling of side chains between themselves.

Main chain is polyimide in fact. Side chains are polyparaphenylenes in fact. Rigidity and linearity of polyimides and polyparaphenylenes provides desired direction of side chains. Because of it, for improving solubility of chains, into them must be introduced relevant side groups. Imide bonds of main chains must stay stable in coupling reactions of side chains. Rings of formed poly[n]catenane are completed from side chains, so after closing of rings (via coupling of side chains between themselves) polyimide main chain must be destroyed selectively (rings must stay stable). For improving solubility of final poly[n]catenanes, rigid-rod oligoimides and chlorinated organic co-solvents (ODCB, EDC etc.) can be used [Ref.9].

At first, we need to construct monomers of main chain. For solubility improving and further protection of imide bonds, main chain monomers (dianhydrides in this case) have bulky substituents. Way to monomer **4** lies through Suzuki coupling bulky substituted boronic acid **2** to aryl bromide **1** and then oxidation of resulted compound **3** by KMnO_4 to dianhydride **4** [Ref 10](Figure 4).

Length of oligomer **9** is very important moment. This is side chain and rings of formed poly[n]catenane are completed from side chains. Mutual bonding of face-to-face oriented side chains possible when distance between their cups are minimal. From geometrical point of view, we need to form equilateral triangle. Because of it, length of oligomer **9** must be approximately (because of molecular scissoring) equal to distance between nodal monomers of main chain, which connected with face-to-face oriented side chains (see Figures 1 & 11). Side chains with substituents play role of rigid and linear branches, located in different (atropisomeric) planes. It is increase free volume and decrease contact area between various molecular fragments and molecules, i.e. it is increase solubility and decrease agglomeration (like in soluble COF [Ref. 11]). We can consider it like bottlebrush polymer [Ref 12].

Side chains of main chain and substituents of side chains improve rigidity and linearity (necessary for correct orientation) via additional steric hindrances and increase persistence length [Ref.13] (with slow scissoring versus fast axial rotation for effective rings closing) [Ref.14]. Oligomer **9** with certain length can be formed via step-growth Suzuki cross-coupling polymerization of boronic acid **7** with aryl bromide **8**. Substituents of oligomer **9** improve solubility, rigidity and play role of donor/acceptor pre-units in final macromolecule (Figure 5). Suitable solvents for reactions include DMF, DMAc, NMP in blends with THF or 1,4-dioxane.

Because of our aim is semiconducting poly[n]catenane, structure of rings should be appropriate. According to General Strategy (Figures 1, 2 & 3) we can construct large cycloparaphenylenes with two opposite meta-phenylenes units (mCPP), which create additional torsional strain of 2 semi-rings [Ref.15] (see Figure 16). This strain decrease free axial rotation of para-phenylenes units and increase conjugation (i.e. decrease HOMO/LUMO gap to point under 4,0 eV) [Ref. 16], with alternation of donor and acceptor units (substitued para-phenylenes units)[Ref.17] in “double-cable” manner [Ref.18]. For the purpose of mCPP synthesis, we can use Wang masked para-phenylenes (compound **18**) strategy [Ref.19] (Figure 6).

Nodal monomer **20** connect main chain with side chains. We need to protect amino group (compound **21**) for correct way of imidization of compound **23** after addition of compound **22** via selective Suzuki coupling to bromine (not to chlorine). PPh₃-ligands are useful in this case of selectivity [Ref.20] and for amine/boronic acid selectivity too [Ref.21] & [Ref.22]. Reaction with **4** give amic acid **24** (Figure 7). Main chain can be formed via step-growth polyimidization of amic acid **24** and free rotation segment **26** (product of imidization of dianhydride **4** with diamine **25**). Boc-deprotection [Ref.23] and polyimidization can realized in one pot in para-chlorophenol/solvent blend with increased temperatures [Ref.10] (Figures 8 & 9).

Next step is side chains additions to main chains. Suzuki coupling with Xphos ligand is useful protocol for attack on sterically hindered chlorines like in this case (Figure 10). Szostak group shown that Pd/XPhos species are failed in oxidative addition to C(O)-N bonds of imides even in absence of more preferred halogen atoms and even with disrupted conjugation of C(O)-N bonds [Ref.24]. There are various examples of compatibility between Pd/XPhos Suzuki coupling protocols conditions and cyclic imide bonds [Ref.25] & [Ref.26]. Resulting polyimide **28** have contact spaces as it shown in Figure 11. Reactions in contact spaces close the rings of future poly[n]catenane. After side chains addition step, we need to cap side chains by dihalogenated arenes **8** in excess, to prevent rings closing (Figure 12). Then, semi-protected masked para-phenylenes units **18** added to side chains and, after boronic acid deprotection (hot hydrolysis) [Ref.27] the rings are closing via Suzuki coupling with high dilution (for effective intramolecular couplings). Pd/Xphos species are effective in intramolecular pre-CPP-macrocyclization [Ref.28] and compatible with Wang masked para-phenylenes units [Ref.29].

Paraphenylenes demasking by DDQ (Figure 13) is compatible with cyclic imide bonds [Ref.30] and with N-Boc and methoxy groups. Next step is mild hydrazinolysis [Ref.31], which compatible with N-Boc-protected [Ref.32] amino groups and with methoxy groups [Ref.33] & [Ref.34]. And finally, after Boc-deprotection of amino groups and further imidization (for construction of side acceptor units) in one pot in para-chlorophenol/solvent blend with increased temperatures or via other imidization strategies [Ref.35] we can receive poly[n]catenated m₂[56]CPP **29** (Figure 14). Separate ring of this structure shown in Figure 15. Rings in diameter are near 5,5 nm.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

amic acid 24

Boc-deprotection of
amino groups
in para-chlorophenol
185°C

26

free rotation segment

polyimidization in
para-chlorophenol
185°C to 250°C
with additional
dehydration

polyimide 27

Figure 9.

polyimide 27

Suzuki coupling:
 $Pd_2(dba)_3$
 XPhos
 K_2CO_3
 DMF/THF

9 (side chain)

polyimide 28

Figure 10.

polyimide 28

Figure 11.

Suzuki coupling

Suzuki coupling

Boronic acid deprotection

Figure 12.

Figure 13.

Boc-deprotection of amino groups

imidization of amino groups

Figure 14.

Figure 15.

Figure 16.

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